

1 **URINARY AND PLASMA-DERIVED EXOSOMES REVEAL A DISTINCT**
2 **MICRORNA SIGNATURE ASSOCIATED WITH ALBUMINURIA IN**
3 **HYPERTENSION**

4 **Running Head:** Exosomal miRNA signature associated with albuminuria

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43 **ABSTRACT**

44 Urinary albumin excretion (UAE) is a marker of cardiovascular risk and renal
45 damage in hypertension (HTN). MicroRNAs (miRNAs) packaged into
46 exosomes (Exo) function as paracrine effectors in cell communication and
47 the kidney is not exempt. This study aimed to state an exosomal miRNA
48 profile/signature associated to HTN with increased UAE and the impact of
49 pro-fibrotic transforming growth factor β 1 (TGF- β 1) on exo-miRNA release.
50 Therefore, Exo samples from HTN patients with/without UAE were isolated
51 and characterized. Three individual and unique small RNA libraries from
52 each subject were prepared (total plasma, urinary and plasma-derived Exo)
53 for next-generation sequencing profiling. Differentially expressed miRNAs
54 were over-represented in KEGG (Kyoto Encyclopedia of Genes and
55 Genomes) pathways and selected miRNAs were validated by RT-qPCR in a
56 confirmation cohort. Thus, a signature of 29 dysregulated circulating miRNAs
57 was identified in UAE hypertensive subjects, regulating 21 pathways.
58 Moreover, changes in the levels of four Exo-miRNAs were validated in a
59 confirmation cohort and found associated with albuminuria. In particular miR-
60 26a, major regulator of TGF- β signaling, was found downregulated in both
61 type of Exo when compared to healthy controls and to HTN
62 normoalbuminurics ($p < 0.01$). Similarly, decreased miR-26a levels were
63 found in podocyte-derived exosomes after TGF- β stress. Our results
64 revealed an exo-miRNA signature associated to albuminuria in HTN. In
65 particular, exo-miR-26a seemed to play a key role in the regulation of TGF- β ,
66 a relevant effector in podocyte damage. These findings support the use of

67 exo-miRNAs as biomarkers of cardiovascular risk progression and
68 therapeutic tools in early kidney damage.

69

70 **Keywords:** exosomes, microRNA, albuminuria, next-generation sequencing,
71 podocytes.

72

73 INTRODUCTION

74 Hypertension (HTN) is a major risk factor for chronic kidney disease (CKD)
75 and persistently increased urinary albumin excretion (UAE) is a marker of
76 cardiovascular risk progression and renal impairment^{1,2}. Its prognostic value
77 in hypertensive cohorts and subgroups of the general population has been
78 well established over the past few years^{3,4}. However, the underlying
79 mechanisms leading to albuminuria progression are incompletely
80 understood.

81 MicroRNAs (miRNAs) are small non-coding RNAs (18-22 nt) that regulate
82 gene expression post-transcriptionally and play an important role in a broad
83 range of biological processes⁵. In the kidney, miRNAs are necessary in renal
84 development, maintenance of renal function and homeostasis processes⁶.
85 Therefore, profiling tissue-specific miRNAs in different biofluids using high-
86 throughput sequencing has been explored to propose new biomarkers of
87 renal diseases^{7,8}. Preliminary evidence has indicated that miRNAs may
88 regulate the progression of glomerular and tubular diseases⁹⁻¹¹.
89 Nevertheless, the mechanisms and role of miRNAs in paracrine crosstalk
90 remain largely unknown^{12,13}.

91 miRNAs can be released into circulation bound to RNA-binding proteins or
92 packaged into extracellular vesicles (EVs) such as exosomes and may
93 function as paracrine effectors in the crosstalk between different cell types in
94 the kidney^{14,15}. Recent studies have demonstrated the role of endothelial
95 exosomal miR-486-5p in reducing ischemic kidney injury and the protective
96 effect of mesenchymal stem cell-derived exosomes through miRNA transfer
97 to renal tubular cells^{16,17}. Our group and others have recently found that low

98 exosomal levels of miR-146a and exosomal proteome signatures are
99 associated with UAE, reflecting changes taking place in the kidney
100 associated to albuminuria^{18,19}. In the glomerulus, along with albuminuria
101 progression podocytes undergo morphological changes leading to
102 modifications in cell architecture, loss of foot processes and detachment from
103 the glomerular basement membrane (GBM)^{20,21}.
104 Thus, we aimed to identify the differentially expressed free and exosomal-
105 transported miRNA profile in urine and plasma from hypertensive patients
106 with albuminuria, to state an exosomal miRNA signature associated with
107 early renal dysfunction. We also assessed the impact of pro-fibrotic TGF- β 1
108 on miRNA release via exosomes in human podocytes.

109

110 **MATERIAL AND METHODS**

111 Note that additional detailed methods are included in the Data Supplement.
112 The authors declare that all supporting data are available within the article
113 (and in the online-only Data Supplement).

114 **Research subjects**

115 This is an observational case control study which included essential
116 hypertensive patients with and without persistent elevated urinary
117 albuminuria (≥ 30 mg/g urinary creatinine)²², such as discovery cohort. A
118 second set of hypertensive patients and a control group of healthy subjects
119 were included as a confirmatory cohort (Figure 1).

120 Therefore, circulating miRNAs in 3 different fractions (total plasma, urinary
121 and plasma-derived exosomes) were assessed by next generation
122 sequencing (NGS) in the discovery cohort and selected miRNA candidates

123 from the dysregulated exo-miRNA profile were subsequently validated by RT-
124 qPCR in the confirmation cohort.

125 The study protocol was approved by the Ethics Committee of the Hospital
126 Clínico Universitario of Valencia in accordance with the Declaration of
127 Helsinki of 1975 as revised in 2008. All subjects signed written informed
128 consent.

129 **Exosome isolation**

130 Exosomes were isolated from urine (Exo-U) and plasma (Exo-P) using a
131 protocol based on sequential ultracentrifugation²³. Briefly, urine samples
132 were initially centrifuged at 2,250 x g for 30 min to remove cells and debris.
133 Cell-free supernatant was centrifuged at 20,000 x g_{av} for 45 min to separate
134 large microvesicles. Next, the supernatant was spun at 110 000 x g_{av} in order
135 to obtain the exosome-enriched pellet.

136 **Small RNA library preparation and next-generation sequencing**

137 Single patient libraries were prepared from 2 µL of total RNA from each
138 condition (total plasma, urinary exosomes or plasma exosomes) using
139 CleanTag Small RNA library preparation kit (TriLink Biotechnologies, US)
140 following an optimized small RNA library preparation protocol to very low
141 input samples previously described²⁴. Pools were quantified, normalized and
142 sequenced on the HiSeq 2000 platform. The raw data were included in the
143 BioProject PRJNA590749 and the corresponding Sequence Read Archive
144 (SRA) and BioSample accession IDs are available in the Supplementary
145 Table S1.

146 **RT-q PCR validation of exosome miRNAs**

147 To validate RNAseq data, we performed RT-qPCR analysis of selected exo-
148 miRNAs related to renal injury and/or presenting specific kidney expression²⁵,
149 using TaqMan™ Advanced miRNA assays (Applied Biosystems, USA)
150 (Table S2). MiRNA selection criteria from NGS data included presence in at
151 least 75% of samples in both study groups, and an absolute \log_2 FC \geq 2. In
152 order to normalize miRNA expression, two miRNAs were selected as internal
153 controls of our experiment (miR-125a and miR-186) due to their stable
154 expression across fractions (total plasma, urinary exosomes, plasma
155 exosomes).

156 Podocyte culture

157 Conditionally human podocytes²⁶ were made quiescent in RPMI 1640
158 medium with 0% FBS for 24 h before stimulation with recombinant human
159 TGF- β 1 (Sigma-Aldrich, US) at several concentrations (5 ng/ml, 10 ng/mL
160 and 15 ng/mL) for up 24 h to assess miR-26a changes in exosomal and
161 cellular fractions.

162 **Statistical analysis**

163 Statistical analyses were performed using GraphPad Prism software
164 (GraphPad, US) and SPSS software (SPSS, US). Results for each variable
165 were tested for normality using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov method. Clinical
166 variables were expressed as the mean \pm standard deviation or percentage.
167 Comparisons between groups for the categorical variables were performed
168 with the Chi-square test and the T-student's test for continuous variables.
169 Mann-Whitney U-test was used to determine significant differences in
170 exosomal miRNA levels among patient groups and for human podocyte
171 experiments. Finally, Spearman's correlation coefficient was used to

172 determine the association between exosomal miRNA levels and UAE. A p-
173 value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

174

175 **RESULTS**

176 **Study population**

177 The discovery cohort included 48 essential hypertensive subjects, 22 with
178 increased UAE and 26 normoalbuminurics. The general characteristics of the
179 patients as well as antihypertensive medication are shown in Table 1.

180 Similarly, a second set of subjects which included 69 hypertensive patients,
181 with and without elevated UAE (Table S3), and 15 healthy controls (age 35 ±
182 7.7, 40% male) were used to confirmatory analysis.

183 **Isolation and characterization of urinary and plasma exosomes**

184 Analysis of exosome preparations by transmission electron microscopy
185 revealed the presence of small round-shaped vesicles with a characteristic
186 size of exosomes (58 ± 20.3 nm). Additionally, single particle analysis
187 confirmed a typical exosome distribution (Figure S1A). Moreover, the vesicle
188 fraction expressed enrichment of well-established exosome protein markers
189 such as tetraspanin CD9 and ESCRT component TSG101, and absence of
190 intracellular compartment markers (Calnexin, GM-130)²⁷ (Figure S1B). At
191 RNA level, both types of exosomes displayed similar profiles with an
192 enrichment of small RNA species, as reported in previous studies (Figure
193 S1C).

194 **Exosomal and plasma miRNAs identified in albuminuria**

195 The first aim was to determine the different circulating miRNA profiles of
196 hypertensive patients associated with albuminuria in three different

197 compartments: total plasma, urinary exosomes and plasma exosomes. For
198 this purpose, we prepared three single, different and unique small RNA
199 libraries from each patient and generated individual libraries for deep
200 sequencing. As shown in the volcano plot (Figure 2A), differential expression
201 analysis of miRNA levels in hypertensive patients with albuminuria (UAE) vs
202 without albuminuria (non UAE) identified a total of 136 significant miRNAs (p
203 < 0.05) (Supplementary Table S4). Interestingly, the miRNA distribution
204 obtained among the biological compartments showed very limited
205 overlapping between exosomal and **plasma** miRNAs, with only 5 of these
206 136 miRNAs common to both groups (Figure 2B).

207 **Urinary and plasma-derived exosomes present a distinct microRNA** 208 **signature associated to albuminuria**

209 In order to focus on the miRNAs strongly associated with albuminuria, a
210 significant cut-off value of absolute $\text{Log}_2\text{FC} \geq 2$ was adopted. From these
211 criteria, 73 miRNAs were finally selected to perform KEGG pathway over-
212 representation analysis which revealed a distinct exo-miRNA signature
213 composed of 29 miRNAs (27 out of 29 contained in the exosomal fraction).
214 The magnitude of change for each miRNA over-represented in the miRNA-
215 KEGG interaction network is shown in Figure 2C (green, upregulated by
216 albuminuria; red, downregulated). Intriguingly, most of the dysregulated
217 miRNAs of the network were reduced in the exosomes of albuminuric
218 subjects.

219 **Exosomal miRNA signature and KEGG pathways**

220 The exo-miRNA signature controlled a total of 21 KEGG pathways (Figure
221 3A). The biological processes most regulated by the differentially expressed

222 miRNAs in albuminuria comprised critical pathways involved in maintaining
223 the glomerular filtration barrier. Hence, three main functional clusters were
224 observed in response to albuminuria: cell adhesion and interaction with the
225 extracellular cell matrix (ECM) (focal adhesion, cell junctions, cell adhesion
226 molecules); modulators in the renal epithelial-mesenchymal transition and
227 ECM expansion (MAPK and TGF- β signaling), and cell proliferation and
228 cytoskeleton rearrangement (cell cycle, apoptosis, actin cytoskeleton
229 regulation) (Figure 3B).

230 Finally, we sought to pinpoint the gene networks regulated only by
231 experimentally validated albuminuria-associated miRNAs. Target genes were
232 predicted using three different *in silico* tools and only the common and
233 highest predicted were used to build a functional regulatory network. We
234 observed individual mRNA targets hit by a particular miRNA along with
235 overlapping shared targets regulated by some of the exo-miRNAs associated
236 with albuminuria (Figure 3C). Interestingly, target prediction in these
237 validated exo-miRNAs identified key elements involved in glomerular injury
238 such as metalloproteinase ADAM9/Mdc9 (GBM disruption)²⁸, cyclin regulator
239 CDK6 and cyclin CDKN1B/p27 (mesangial and podocyte hypertrophy)^{29,30},
240 Smad1 and Smurf2 (TGF- β induced pro-fibrotic signaling)³¹, and CRK/p38
241 (MAPK signaling activation)³².

242 Together these results suggest a deleterious remodeling of GBM in
243 albuminuria, including changes in ECM composition, phenotype and size of
244 glomerular endothelial cells, mesangial cells and podocytes, which could lead
245 to progressive deterioration of filtration barrier integrity.

246 **Validated exosomal miRNAs are associated with urinary albumin**
247 **excretion**

248 To confirm the dysregulation of specific exo-miRNAs in response to
249 albuminuria, 8 miRNAs from the exo-miRNA signature were selected for RT-
250 qPCR in a confirmation cohort and healthy control group (CNT): miR-143-3p
251 (urinary exosomes); miR-126-3p, miR-26a-5p, miR-144-3p, miR-191-5p,
252 miR-220a-3p, miR-222-3p, miR-423-5p (plasma exosomes) and miR-26a-5p
253 (both Exo types). Our results confirmed the differences in exo-miRNA levels
254 of albuminuric patients obtained by NGS compared to CNT and
255 normoalbuminuric groups for miR-191-5p (increased in UAE group, $p <$
256 0.001), miR-222-3p (decreased in UAE group, $p < 0.001$ and $p < 0.01$,
257 respectively) and miR-126-3p (decreased in UAE group, $p < 0.001$) in the
258 plasma exosome fraction, and miR-26a for both urine and plasma exosomes
259 (decreased in UAE group, $p < 0.001$ and $p < 0.01$, respectively) (Figure 4A).
260 The decrease in urinary exosomal miR-26a is still observed when their levels
261 are normalized by urinary creatinine ($p < 0.01$). Only miR-126-3p levels in
262 plasma exosomes and miR-26a-5p in both exosome types, were significantly
263 different between non-UAE and healthy controls ($p < 0.001$ and $p < 0.01$,
264 respectively). Conversely, no significant changes were found in the amount
265 of plasma exo-miR-144-3p, miR-200a-3p or miR-423-5p, and urinary exo-
266 miR-143-3p was detected in less than 50% of the samples (Supplemental
267 Figure S2).

268 Moreover, validated exo-miRNA levels were correlated with UAE in all
269 hypertensive subjects, finding significant inverse association for miR-26a
270 expression, both in urinary and plasma exosomes ($r = -0.42$, $p < 0.01$; $r = -$

271 0.47, $p < 0.001$), and miR-222-3p in plasma exosomes ($r = -0.43$, $p < 0.01$).
272 In contrast, a positive correlation was obtained for miR-191-5p and miR-126-
273 3p levels ($r = 0.58$ and $r = 0.67$, respectively, $p < 0.0001$) (Figure 4B).
274 Downregulation of exosomal miR-26a by TGF- β 1 in human podocytes
275 As TGF- β 1 signaling was a biological process regulated by the differentially
276 expressed miR-26a in our patients, we analyzed the impact of TGF- β 1 on
277 exosomal miR-26a release by podocytes using RT-qPCR. Stimulation with
278 TGF- β 1 (5 – 15 ng / mL) significantly reduced miR-26a levels in exosomes
279 from podocytes: a 2.23, 1.96 and 1.7-fold decrease was observed ($p < 0.001$
280 and $p < 0.05$, respectively) (Figure 5). Interestingly, no significant changes in
281 miR-26a levels were found directly on podocytes following TGF- β 1 stress.

282

283 **DISCUSSION**

284 In the present study, an altered profile of 29 miRNAs was observed in
285 hypertensive albuminuric patients, predominantly found in plasma exosomes,
286 which participated in regulating 21 biological processes, most of them
287 implicated in mechanisms inducing renal damage. Subsequently, some of the
288 exo-miRNAs obtained by NGS were further validated in a confirmation cohort
289 and their levels correlated with UAE. In particular, miR-26a, a major regulator
290 of TGF- β signaling, was the only miRNA downregulated in the albuminuric
291 subjects for both, urinary and plasma-derived exosomes. As proof of
292 concept, human podocytes exposed to TGF- β 1 *in vitro* showed a significant
293 decrease in exo-miR-26a release, but not at cellular level, suggesting a
294 selective sorting of miRNAs into exosomes.

295 A key feature of the present study was the strategy applied. Our
296 multicompartment approach was intended to provide a global circulating
297 miRNA profile or signature associated with albuminuria. The study of
298 EV/exosome-carried miRNAs has gained interest in the last few years,
299 offering more reliable signatures than conventional studies limited to a single,
300 mostly unspecific biofluid sample analysis³³⁻³⁶. By combining the differentially
301 expressed miRNAs found in total plasma, urinary and plasma-derived
302 exosomes, we sought greater insight into the interconnected processes
303 occurring in the kidney of hypertensive subjects. Thus, the differentially
304 expressed miRNAs associated with albuminuria were mainly different among
305 biological fractions and showed limited overlapping, supporting the selective
306 sorting of specific miRNAs into exosomes compared to the whole miRNA
307 circulating pool^{37,38}. Previous works showed unique miRNA content in
308 specific biological fractions^{17,39}. In agreement with the findings of the present
309 study, Xie *et al.* showed differences in the plasma exo-miRNA profile
310 associated CKD, which shares some altered miRNAs with the increased UAE
311 group (e.g. miR-143-3p, miR-429) as well as enriched pathways (e.g.
312 fibrosis, ECM modulation)⁴⁰.
313 Our over-representation analysis showed that most of the enriched biological
314 processes were well-known modulators involved in the onset and
315 progression of CKD, affecting both glomerular and tubular components. For
316 instance TGF- β , a pro-fibrotic cytokine synthesized by different renal
317 components, has been found upregulated at very early stages of renal
318 disease, inducing glomerulosclerosis and tubulointerstitial fibrosis via Smad
319 and MAPK pathways⁴¹. Similarly, “focal adhesions” and “ECM receptor

320 interaction” were top-regulated pathways by the altered miRNA profile. In
321 order to adhere to the GBM, podocytes and endothelial cells use specific
322 anchoring points that function as signaling hubs⁴², controlling cell behavior
323 and morphology and regulating actin cytoskeleton⁴³. Our group has also
324 recently described that albuminuric patients showed reduced mRNA levels of
325 podocyte-specific genes and higher levels of nephrin in urinary sediment²¹. In
326 line with this observation, the dysregulated exo-miRNA signature found
327 seems to be involved in a progressive podocyte dedifferentiation, loss of foot
328 processes and consequent detachment from the GBM.

329 Among the 29 miRNAs of the network, many of them (e.g. miR-30a-5p, miR-
330 191-5p, miR-26a-5p, miR-126-3p, miR-200b-3p, miR-143-3p) have already
331 been reported for their implication in renal pathophysiology^{11,30,40}. Eight
332 candidate exo-miRNAs were selected and further validated by RT-qPCR but
333 only four were found to be significantly altered in albuminuria. In addition, we
334 found a correlation of exo-miRNA levels and UAE in the hypertensive
335 confirmation cohort, suggesting a molecular phenotype that may represent
336 early subjacent biological changes in those individuals.

337 Validated exo-miRNAs appeared to play important roles in renal
338 homeostasis. EV-associated miR-222-3p, downregulated in UAE group,
339 protected mesangial and endothelial cells in hyperglycemia^{44,45} whereas miR-
340 191-5p, produced by mesangial cells in the glomeruli and upregulated in
341 UAE, has been also found to be increased in children with nephrotic
342 syndrome^{25,46}. MiR-126-3p is enriched in endothelial cells and facilitates
343 vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) signaling, controlling also vascular
344 cell adhesion-1 (VCAM-1) expression in the kidney upon inflammation⁴⁷, both

345 pathways strongly altered in the UAE miRNA profile. Interestingly, exo-miR-
346 126 levels were augmented in our population along with cardiovascular risk
347 and UAE progression. This fact could be in line with previous studies
348 implicating higher levels of circulating endothelial EVs and miR-126 as
349 hallmark for vascular damage and increased cardiovascular events^{48,49}.
350 Remarkably, miR-26a-5p was the only miRNA downregulated in both types
351 of exosomes. This miRNA, an important modulator of glomerular
352 development and structure⁵⁰, was found decreased in patients with
353 secondary hypertension and its restoration showed renoprotective effects in
354 swine⁵¹. In addition, miR-26a has been also reported as abundant in urinary
355 exosomes and adipose stem cell-derived EVs, capable to restore GBM
356 integrity and improve pathological lesions in diabetic nephropathy^{10,52}. An
357 intriguing progressive reduction of exo-miR-26a levels according to the
358 hypertension status and UAE was found in our cohort, in both urine and
359 plasma exosomes. Similarly, depletion of miR-26a in renal biopsies has been
360 associated with a decline in renal function⁹. MiR-26a inhibits ECM synthesis
361 in podocytes by targeting connective tissue growth factor (CTGF) and has
362 been used to reduce TGF- β 1-induced fibrosis in diabetic nephropathy^{9,30}.
363 Moreover, it also regulates VEGF-A expression indirectly via PIK3C2 α ⁴⁷, key
364 protein to preserve integrity and architecture of the glomerular filtration
365 barrier¹².
366 It has been shown that TGF- β stimulation modifies exosomal cargo, altering
367 paracrine communication and phenotype in cardiomyocytes and aortic
368 endothelial cells^{53,54}. In the glomeruli, TGF- β mediates podocytopenia and
369 ECM expansion⁴¹. Our *in vitro* approach showed a significant decrease in

370 exosomal miR-26a levels in podocytes exposed to TGF- β 1. Similarly, there
371 was a progressive decline in miR-26a levels in urinary and plasma exosomes
372 obtained from hypertensives, especially those with UAE. These findings
373 strongly support that regulation of (exosomal) miR-26a and miR-126 is critical
374 in maintaining kidney homeostasis, leading to the hypothesis that exo-miRNA
375 levels are regulated in the kidney microenvironment by several mechanisms
376 all along the *continuum* of the disease. Thus, exo-miRNAs are likely to be
377 found as new mediators bridging the gap in paracrine cell crosstalk within the
378 integrative glomerular barrier complex^{13,55}.

379 Our study has several strengths and weaknesses. The number of
380 participants enrolled in the study could be a limitation but the inclusion of a
381 confirmation cohort strengthens our results. Additionally, the origin of
382 participants recruited might be a limitation and further research using larger
383 and independent cohorts will be warranted to confirm the exo-miRNA
384 signature found. Nevertheless, the multicompartiment approach applied in
385 this study, combining miRNA profiling in three different biological fractions,
386 has brought greater insight into specific pathways early activated in the
387 kidney of hypertensive subjects developing albuminuria. Similarly, an attempt
388 to assess the impact of pro-fibrotic stress on exo-miRNA paracrine
389 glomerular communication was made by quantifying miR-26a release into
390 podocyte-derived exosomes.

391 In conclusion, our study found an exo-miRNA profile associated with
392 albuminuria that targets some critical pathways of filtration barrier integrity,
393 suggesting a potential role for exosomal miRNAs to report early renal
394 damage and to be used as new therapeutic agents to preserve or restore

395 glomerular function. The particular impact of the exo-miRNA signature found
396 (miR-26a-5p, miR-191-5p, miR-222-3p, miR-126-3p) on identified pathways
397 and targets may shed light on better understanding the diverse progression
398 of renal damage in hypertension and identifying new potential therapeutic
399 strategies.

400

401 **Perspectives**

402 This study demonstrated that the circulating exosomal miRNome represents
403 an **accurate** source of biomarkers for cardiovascular progression and target
404 organ damage. Dysregulated exo-miRNAs targeted signalling pathways
405 involved in the architecture of the glomerular filtration barrier and vascular
406 integrity such as TGF- β and VEGF. *In vitro* studies showed that exo-miRNA
407 levels in podocytes can be influenced by TGF- β stress, that mediates
408 podocytopenia and ECM expansion in kidney disease. Thus, the altered exo-
409 miRNA profile may constitute alternative therapeutic targets for the control of
410 albuminuria progression and new therapeutic agents to preserve or restore
411 glomerular function.

412

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426

427 **Disclosures**

428 None.

429 **REFERENCES**

- 430 1. Arnlöv J, Evans JC, Meigs JB, Wang TJ, Fox CS, Levy D, Benjamin
431 EJ, D'Agostino RB, Vasan RS. Low-grade albuminuria and incidence
432 of cardiovascular disease events in nonhypertensive and nondiabetic
433 individuals: The Framingham heart study. *Circulation*. 2005;112:969-
434 975.
- 435 2. Kong X, Jia X, Wei Y, Cui M, Wang Z, Tang L, Li W, Zhu Z, Chen P,
436 Xu D. Association between microalbuminuria and subclinical
437 atherosclerosis evaluated by carotid artery intima-media in elderly
438 patients with normal renal function. *BMC Nephrol*. 2012;13:37.
- 439 3. Gerstein HC, Mann JF, Yi Q, Zinman B, Dinneen SF, Hoogwerf B,
440 Hallé JP, Young J, Rashkow A, Joyce C, Nawaz S, Yusuf S; HOPE
441 Study Investigators. Albuminuria and risk of cardiovascular events,
442 death, and heart failure in diabetic and nondiabetic individuals. *JAMA*.
443 2001;286:421-426.
- 444 4. Pascual JM, Rodilla E, Costa JA, Garcia-Esrich M, Gonzalez C,
445 Redon J. Prognostic value of microalbuminuria during
446 antihypertensive treatment in essential hypertension. *Hypertension*.
447 2014;64:1228-1234.
- 448 5. Ambros V. The functions of animal microRNAs. *Nature*. 2004;431:350-
449 355.
- 450 6. Chandrasekaran K, Karolina DS, Sepramaniam S, Arumugam A,
451 Wintour EM, Bertram JF, Jeyaseelan K. Role of microRNAs in kidney
452 homeostasis and disease. *Kidney Int*. 2012;81:617-627.

- 453 7. Lorenzen JM, Thum T. Circulating and urinary microRNAs in kidney
454 disease. *Clin J Am Soc Nephrol.* 2012;7:1528-1533.
- 455 8. Cheng L, Sun X, Scicluna BJ, Coleman BM, Hill AF. Characterization
456 and deep sequencing analysis of exosomal and non-exosomal miRNA
457 in human urine. *Kidney Int.* 2014;86:433-444.
- 458 9. Koga K, Yokoi H, Mori K, Kasahara M, Kuwabara T, Imamaki H, Ishii
459 A, Mori KP, Kato Y, Ohno S, et al. MicroRNA-26a inhibits TGF-beta-
460 induced extracellular matrix protein expression in podocytes by
461 targeting CTGF and is downregulated in diabetic nephropathy.
462 *Diabetologia.* 2015;58:2169-2180.
- 463 10. Gracia T, Wang X, Su Y, Norgett EE, Williams TL, Moreno P, Micklem
464 G, Karet Frankl FE. Urinary exosomes contain MicroRNAs capable of
465 paracrine modulation of tubular transporters in kidney. *Sci Rep.*
466 2017;7:40601.
- 467 11. Müller-Deile J, Gellrich F, Schenk H, Schroder P, Nyström J, Lorenzen
468 J, Haller H, Schiffer M. Overexpression of TGF-beta inducible
469 microRNA-143 in zebrafish leads to impairment of the glomerular
470 filtration barrier by targeting proteoglycans. *Cell Physiol Biochem.*
471 2016;40:819-830.
- 472 12. Sison K, Eremina V, Baelde H, Min W, Hirashima M, Fantus IG,
473 Quaggin SE. Glomerular structure and function require paracrine, not
474 autocrine, VEGF-VEGFR-2 signaling. *J Am Soc Nephrol.*
475 2010;21:1691-1701.
- 476 13. Haraldsson BS. The endothelium as part of the integrative glomerular
477 barrier complex. *Kidney Int.* 2014;85:8-11.

- 478 14. Yáñez-Mó M, Siljander PR, Andreu Z, Zavec AB, Borràs FE, Buzas EI,
479 Buzas K, Casal E, Cappello F, Carvalho J. Biological properties of
480 extracellular vesicles and their physiological functions. *J Extracell*
481 *Vesicles*. 2015;4:27066.
- 482 15. Erdbrugger U, Le TH. Extracellular vesicles as a novel diagnostic and
483 research tool for patients with HTN and kidney disease. *Am J Physiol*
484 *Renal Physiol*. 2019;317:F641-F647.
- 485 16. Viñas JL, Burger D, Zimpelmann J, Haneef R, Knoll W, Campbell P,
486 Gutsol A, Carter A, Allan DS, Burns KD. Transfer of microRNA-486-5p
487 from human endothelial colony forming cell-derived exosomes
488 reduces ischemic kidney injury. *Kidney Int*. 2016;90:1238-1250.
- 489 17. Collino F, Pomatto M, Bruno S, Lindoso RS, Tapparo M, Sicheng W,
490 Quesenberry P, Camussi G. Exosome and microvesicle-enriched
491 fractions isolated from mesenchymal stem cells by gradient separation
492 showed different molecular signatures and functions on renal tubular
493 epithelial cells. *Stem Cell Rev*. 2017;13:226-243.
- 494 18. Perez-Hernandez J, Olivares D, Forner MJ, Ortega A, Solaz E,
495 Martinez F, Chaves FJ, Redon J, Cortes R. Urinary exosome miR-
496 146a is a potential marker of albuminuria in essential hypertension. *J*
497 *Transl Med*. 2018;16:228.
- 498 19. Gonzalez-Calero L, Martínez PJ, Martín-Lorenzo M, Baldan-Martin M,
499 Ruiz-Hurtado G, de la Cuesta F, Calvo E, Segura J, Lopez JA,
500 Vázquez J, Barderas MG, Ruilope LM, Vivanco F, Alvarez-Llamas G.
501 Urinary exosomes reveal protein signatures in hypertensive patients
502 with albuminuria. *Oncotarget*. 2017;8:44217-44231.

- 503 20. Cybulsky AV, Takano T, Papillon J, Guillemette J, Herzenberg AM,
504 Kennedy CR. Podocyte injury and albuminuria in mice with podocyte-
505 specific overexpression of the Ste20-like kinase, SLK. *Am J Pathol.*
506 2010;177:2290-9.
- 507 21. Perez-Hernandez J, Olivares MD, Solaz E, Martinez F, Martínez-
508 Hervas S, Pichler G, Chaves FJ, Redon J, Cortes R. Urinary
509 podocyte-associated molecules and albuminuria in hypertension. *J*
510 *Hypertens.* 2018;36:1712-1718.
- 511 22. Mancia G, Fagard R, Narkiewicz K, Redon J, Zanchetti A, Böhm M,
512 Christiaens T, Cifkova R, De Backer G, Dominiczak A, et al; Task
513 Force for the Management of Arterial Hypertension of the European
514 Society of Hypertension and the European Society of Cardiology.
515 2013 ESH/ESC Practice Guidelines for the Management of Arterial
516 Hypertension. *Blood Press.* 2014;23:3-16
- 517 23. Perez-Hernandez J, Forner MJ, Pinto C, Chaves FJ, Cortes R, Redon
518 J. Increased urinary exosomal MicroRNAs in patients with systemic
519 lupus erythematosus. *PLoS One.* 2015;10:e0138618.
- 520 24. Olivares D, Perez-Hernandez J, Perez-Gil D, Chaves FJ, Redon J,
521 Cortes R. Optimization of small RNA library preparation protocol from
522 human urinary exosomes. *J Transl Med.* 2020;18:132.
- 523 25. Müller-Deile J, Dannenberg J, Liu P, Lorenzen J, Nyström J, Thum T,
524 Schiffer M. Identification of cell and disease specific microRNAs in
525 glomerular pathologies. *J Cell Mol Med.* 2019;23:3927-3939.
- 526 26. Saleem MA, O'Hare MJ, Reiser J, Coward RJ, Inward CD, Farren T,
527 Xing CY, Ni L, Mathieson PW, Mundel P. A conditionally immortalized

528 human podocyte cell line demonstrating nephrin and podocin
529 expression. *J Am Soc Nephrol.* 2002;13:630-638.

530 27. Théry C, Witwer KW, Aikawa E, Alcaraz MJ, Anderson JD,
531 Andriantsitohaina R, Antoniou A, Arab T, Archer F, Atkin-Smith GK, et
532 al; Minimal information for studies of extracellular vesicles 2018
533 (MISEV2018): A position statement of the international society for
534 extracellular vesicles and update of the MISEV2014 guidelines. *J*
535 *Extracell Vesicles.* 2018;7:1535750.

536 28. Mahimkar RM, Baricos WH, Visaya O, Pollock AS, Lovett DH.
537 Identification, cellular distribution and potential function of the
538 metalloprotease-disintegrin MDC9 in the kidney. *J Am Soc Nephrol.*
539 2000;11:595-603.

540 29. Wolf G, Schanze A, Stahl RA, Shankland SJ, Amann K. p27(Kip1)
541 knockout mice are protected from diabetic nephropathy: Evidence for
542 p27(Kip1) haplotype insufficiency. *Kidney Int.* 2005;68:1583-1589.

543 30. Kölling M, Kaucsar T, Schauerte C, Hübner A, Dettling A, Park JK,
544 Busch M, Wulff X, Meier M, Scherf K, et al. Therapeutic miR-21
545 silencing ameliorates diabetic kidney disease in mice. *Mol Ther.*
546 2017;25:165-180.

547 31. Icli B, Wara AK, Moslehi J, Sun X, Plovie E, Cahill M, Marchini JF,
548 Schissler A, Padera RF, Shi J, et al. MicroRNA-26a regulates
549 pathological and physiological angiogenesis by targeting BMP/SMAD1
550 signaling. *Circ Res.* 2013;113:1231-1241.

551 32. Koshikawa M, Mukoyama M, Mori K, Suganami T, Sawai K, Yoshioka
552 T, Nagae T, Yokoi H, Kawachi H, Shimizu F, Sugawara A, Nakao K.

553 Role of p38 mitogen-activated protein kinase activation in podocyte
554 injury and proteinuria in experimental nephrotic syndrome. *J Am Soc*
555 *Nephrol.* 2005;16:2690-2701.

556 33. Zheng Z, Guan M, Jia Y, Wang D, Pang R, Lv F, Xiao Z, Wang L,
557 Zhang H, Xue Y. The coordinated roles of miR-26a and miR-30c in
558 regulating TGFbeta1-induced epithelial-to-mesenchymal transition in
559 diabetic nephropathy. *Sci Rep.* 2016;6:37492.

560 34. Witwer KW. Circulating microRNA biomarker studies: Pitfalls and
561 potential solutions. *Clin Chem.* 2015;61:56-63.

562 35. Gámez-Valero A, Campdelacreu J, Vilas D, Ispuerto L, Reñé R,
563 Álvarez R, Armengol MP, Borràs FE, Beyer K. Exploratory study on
564 microRNA profiles from plasma-derived extracellular vesicles in
565 alzheimer's disease and dementia with lewy bodies. *Transl*
566 *Neurodegener.* 2019;8:31.

567 36. Wang H, Jiang D, Li W, Xiang X, Zhao J, Yu B, Wang C, He Z, Zhu L,
568 Yang Y. Evaluation of serum extracellular vesicles as noninvasive
569 diagnostic markers of glioma. *Theranostics.* 2019;9:5347-5358.

570 37. Vickers KC, Palmisano BT, Shoucri BM, Shamburek RD, Remaley AT.
571 MicroRNAs are transported in plasma and delivered to recipient cells
572 by high-density lipoproteins. *Nat Cell Biol.* 2011;13:423-433.

573 38. Villarroya-Beltri C, Gutiérrez-Vázquez C, Sánchez-Cabo F, Pérez-
574 Hernández D, Vázquez J, Martín-Cofreces N, Martínez-Herrera DJ,
575 Pascual-Montano A, Mittelbrunn M, Sánchez-Madrid F. Sumoylated
576 hnRNP A2B1 controls the sorting of miRNAs into exosomes through
577 binding to specific motifs. *Nat Commun.* 2013;4:2980.

- 578 39. Li H, Ouyang Y, Sadovsky E, Parks WT, Chu T, Sadovsky Y. Unique
579 microRNA Signals in Plasma Exosomes from Pregnancies
580 Complicated by Preeclampsia. *Hypertension*. 2020;75:762-771.
- 581 40. Xie JX, Fan X, Drummond CA, Majumder R, Xie Y, Chen T, Liu L,
582 Haller ST, Brewster PS, Dworkin LD, Cooper CJ, Tian J. MicroRNA
583 profiling in kidney disease: Plasma versus plasma-derived exosomes.
584 *Gene*. 2017;627:1-8.
- 585 41. Loeffler I, Wolf G. Transforming growth factor-beta and the
586 progression of renal disease. *Nephrol Dial Transplant*. 2014;29 Suppl
587 1:i37-i45.
- 588 42. Lennon R, Randles MJ, Humphries MJ. The importance of podocyte
589 adhesion for a healthy glomerulus. *Front Endocrinol (Lausanne)*.
590 2014;5:160.
- 591 43. Perico L, Conti S, Benigni A, Remuzzi G. Podocyte-actin dynamics in
592 health and disease. *Nat Rev Nephrol*. 2016;12:692-710.
- 593 44. Jansen F, Yang X, Baumann K, Przybilla D, Schmitz T, Flender A,
594 Paul K, Alhusseiny A, Nickenig G, Werner N. Endothelial
595 microparticles reduce ICAM-1 expression in a microRNA-222-
596 dependent mechanism. *J Cell Mol Med*. 2015;19:2202-2214.
- 597 45. Gallo S, Gili M, Lombardo G, Rossetti A, Rosso A, Dentelli P, Togliatto
598 G, Deregibus MC, Taverna D, Camussi G, Brizzi MF. Stem cell-
599 derived, microRNA-carrying extracellular vesicles: A novel approach to
600 interfering with mesangial cell collagen production in a hyperglycaemic
601 setting. *PLoS One*. 2016;11:e0162417.

- 602 46. Luo Y, Wang C, Chen X, Zhong T, Cai X, Chen S, Shi Y, Hu J, Guan
603 X, Xia Z, Wang J, Zen K, Zhang CY, Zhang C. Increased serum and
604 urinary microRNAs in children with idiopathic nephrotic syndrome. *Clin*
605 *Chem.* 2013;59:658-666.
- 606 47. Asgeirsdóttir SA, van Solingen C, Kurniati NF, Zwiers PJ, Heeringa P,
607 van Meurs M, Satchell SC, Saleem MA, Mathieson PW, Banas B,
608 Kamps JA, Rabelink TJ, van Zonneveld AJ, Molema G. MicroRNA-126
609 contributes to renal microvascular heterogeneity of VCAM-1 protein
610 expression in acute inflammation. *Am J Physiol Renal Physiol.*
611 2012;302:F1630-9.
- 612 48. Rautou PE, Vion AC, Amabile N, Chironi G, Simon A, Tedgui A,
613 Boulanger CM. Microparticles, vascular function, and
614 atherothrombosis. *Circ Res.* 2011;109:593-606.
- 615 49. Zampetaki A, Willeit P, Tilling L, Drozdov I, Prokopi M, Renard JM,
616 Mayr A, Weger S, Schett G, Shah A, Boulanger CM, Willeit J,
617 Chowienczyk PJ, Kiechl S, Mayr M. Prospective study on circulating
618 MicroRNAs and risk of myocardial infarction. *J Am Coll Cardiol.*
619 2012;60:290-9.
- 620 50. Ho J, Ng KH, Rosen S, Dostal A, Gregory RI, Kreidberg JA. Podocyte-
621 specific loss of functional microRNAs leads to rapid glomerular and
622 tubular injury. *J Am Soc Nephrol.* 2008;19:2069-2075.
- 623 51. Zhu XY, Ebrahimi B, Eirin A, Woollard JR, Tang H, Jordan KL, Ofori
624 M, Saad A, Herrmann SM, Dietz AB, Textor SC, Lerman A, Lerman
625 LO. Renal Vein Levels of MicroRNA-26a Are Lower in the Poststenotic
626 Kidney. *J Am Soc Nephrol.* 2015;26:1378-1388.

- 627 52. Duan Y, Luo Q, Wang Y, Ma Y, Chen F, Zhu X, Shi J. Adipose
628 mesenchymal stem cell-derived extracellular vesicles containing
629 microRNA-26a-5p target TLR4 and protect against diabetic
630 nephropathy. *J Biol Chem.* 2020;295:12868-12884.
- 631 53. Jarad M, Kuczynski EA, Morrison J, Vilorio-Petit AM, Coomber BL.
632 Release of endothelial cell associated VEGFR2 during TGF- β
633 modulated angiogenesis in vitro. *BMC Cell Biol.* 2017;18:10.
- 634 54. Basma H, Johanson AN, Dhar K, Anderson D, Qiu F, Rennard S,
635 Lowes BD. TGF- β induces a heart failure phenotype via fibroblasts
636 exosome signaling. *Heliyon.* 2019;5:e02633.
- 637 55. Müller-Deile J, Schenk H, Schroder P, Schulze K, Bolaños-Palmieri P,
638 Siegerist F, Endlich N, Haller H, Schiffer M. Circulating factors cause
639 proteinuria in parabiotic zebrafish. *Kidney Int.* 2019;96:342-349.
- 640

641 **Novelty and significance**

642 **What is new?**

- 643 • This is the first study to profile the circulating miRNome in three
644 different biofluids from hypertensive patients with/without albuminuria.
- 645 • An altered exosomal-miRNA signature (miR-26a-5p, miR-191-5p,
646 miR-222-3p and miR-126-3p) was validated in a confirmation cohort
647 and associated to albumin excretion.

648 **What is relevant?**

- 649 • The dysregulated exo-miRNA profile targeted critical pathways for the
650 glomerular filtration barrier and vascular integrity, such as TGF- β and
651 VEGF signalling.
- 652 • In vitro TGF- β stress reduced exosomal miR-26a released by
653 podocytes, suggesting an impaired regulation of exo-miRNAs in the
654 kidney microenvironment during albuminuria progression.

655 **Summary**

- 656 • Our study revealed an altered circulating exosomal miRNA profile, that
657 regulates specific pathways implicated in renal and vascular damage
658 and evolves during hypertension progression.

659

660

661 **FIGURE LEGENDS**

662 **Figure 1. Schematic overview of the strategy used to identify an Exo-**
663 **miRNA signature associated with albuminuria.** Our study design involved
664 a discovery phase including hypertensives (n=48) with urinary albumin
665 excretion (UAE) or normoalbuminuric (Non UAE) by Small RNA sequencing.
666 In a second confirmation stage with a large hypertensive cohort (n=69),
667 including urinary albumin excretion (UAE) or normoalbuminuric (Non UAE)
668 and healthy controls (CNT, n=15), 4 miRNAs were finally validated by RT-
669 qPCR. Exo-P: exosome plasma; Exo-U: exosome urine.

670 **Figure 2. RNA-Seq differential expression analysis of miRNAs obtained**
671 **in urinary exosomes, plasma exosomes and total plasma of**
672 **hypertensive patients with vs without albuminuria.** A) Volcano plot
673 depicts the significantly altered miRNAs found (p -value < 0.05). Each dot
674 represents a miRNA, downregulated are in red (\log_2 fold-change < 2),
675 upregulated in green (\log_2 fold-change > 2) and unchanged in gray. B) Venn
676 diagram shows the total differentially expressed miRNAs according to their
677 fraction/origin. Overlapping miRNAs among biological fractions are indicated.
678 C) Charts give the fold change expression of the 29 miRNAs obtained in the
679 KEGG pathway over-representation analysis (up or downregulated miRNAs
680 in albuminuria with an absolute \log_2 (fold-change) > 2 are shown).

681 **Figure 3. KEGG pathways over-represented in the differentially**
682 **expressed miRNAs associated with albuminuria.** A) miRNA-KEGG
683 pathway interaction network of significantly altered miRNAs. The size of the
684 nodes increases in relation to the number of edges (network degree). The
685 over-represented KEGG pathways are represented in grey squares, whereas

686 miRNAs with differential expression are shown in circles and those validated
687 by RT-qPCR in triangles. Validated nodes are shown with solid edges while
688 the rest are presented as dash edges. B) Top related KEGG pathways and
689 the associated p-value. C) The mRNA that encode proteins related to the
690 over-represented KEGG pathways are shown in yellow, whereas the mRNA
691 targets of other pathways are shown in gray and the size of the nodes
692 increases in relation to the number of edges (network degree).

693 **Figure 4. Validation of exosomal miRNA (exo-miRNA) associated with**
694 **albuminuria levels in the confirmation cohort.** A) Expression levels of
695 selected exo-miRNAs by RT-qPCR in hypertensive patients and healthy
696 controls (CNT). Absolute copy number was normalized to miR-125a and
697 miR-186 internal controls. Data was compared using Mann-Whitney U-test.
698 B) Correlation between exo-miRNA levels and urinary albumin excretion in all
699 hypertensive patients. Inverse associations were found for miR-26a (both
700 urinary and plasma exosomes) and miR-222 expression, whereas direct
701 association were obtained for miR-126 and miR-191 levels. Spearman's
702 correlation coefficient test was used. Exo-P: plasma exosomes; Exo-U:
703 urinary exosomes; UAE: Urinary albumin excretion. ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p <$
704 0.001 .

705 **Figure 5. Exosomal miR-26a is downregulated after TGF- β 1 stimulation**
706 **in human podocytes.** Differentiated podocytes were treated with TGF- β 1 (5
707 ng/ml, 10 ng/ml and 15 ng/ml) (grey bars) or vehicle for 24 h (white bars).
708 MiR-26a levels in podocytes and exosomes obtained from conditioned media
709 were examined by RT-qPCR (n=4 independent experiments). Relative

710 expression was calculated using the $\Delta\Delta C_T$ method and spike-in cel-miR-39 for
711 normalization. **p < 0.01; *p<0.05. Data are expressed as mean \pm SEM.
712

713 **Table 1.** Clinical characteristics of patient groups.

Variables	Albuminuria (UAE) (n = 22)	Normoalbuminuria (Non UAE) (n = 26)
Age (years)	52.2 ± 8.3	55.0 ± 5.3
Gender (male)	68.2 %	65.4 %
Systolic blood pressure (mmHg)	136 ± 15	136 ± 24
Diastolic blood pressure (mmHg)	85 ± 10	87 ± 14
Pulse pressure (mmHg)	51 ± 12	48 ± 17
Glucose (mg/dL)	122 ± 46	119 ± 41
Glycated hemoglobin (%)	6.6 ± 1.2	6.0 ± 0.9
Total Cholesterol (mg/dL)	200 ± 34*	173 ± 29
LDL (mg/dL)	128 ± 30*	108 ± 25
HDL (mg/dL)	51 ± 14	50 ± 10
Triglycerides (mg/dL)	153 ± 78	127 ± 60
Plasma creatinine (mg/dL)	0.87 ± 0.30	0.90 ± 0.22
Glomerular filtration rate (mL/min/1.73 m ²)	96 ± 27	87 ± 19
Waist (cm)	108 ± 14	100 ± 12

Central obesity (%)	55	40
Body mass index (kg/m ²)	32 ± 7	30 ± 5
Obesity (%)	55	39.3
Obesity grade (%)		
Grade I	29	20
Grade II	9	12
Grade III	14	8
Diabetes (%)	41	35
Dyslipidemia (%)	86	85
Smoking (%)	55	48
Ex-Smoking (%)	25	12
Urinary albumin excretion/Creatinine (mg/g)	146.4 ± 144.3†	3.1 ± 1.7
Antihypertensive treatment (%)		
ARB	95	92
CCB	36	38
Diuretics	68	62
Statins	32	8
Number antihypertensive drugs		

(%)		
1	14	23
2	54	50
3	32	27

714 Data are expressed as mean \pm SD, unless otherwise noted. Glomerular
715 filtration rate calculated by Modification of Diet in Renal Disease (MDRD)
716 formula. ARB: Angiotensin II Receptor Blockers; CCB: Calcium Channel
717 Blockers; HDL, high-density lipoprotein; LDL, high-density lipoprotein;
718 MDRD: Modification of Diet in Renal Disease. Comparisons between groups:
719 * $p < 0.01$, † $p < 0.001$.

720

721